

Notas breves

Circulus mainguyi nomen novum for Circulus depressus
Rubio & Rolán, 2022, p. 362

Circulus mainguyi nomen novum para Circulus depressus Rubio &
Rolán, 2022, pág. 362

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KEY WORDS: *Circulus depressus*, *Circulus mainguyi*, *nomen novum*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Circulus depressus*, *Circulus mainguyi*, *nomen novum*.

After the publication of our book on Indo-Pacific Vitrinellidae (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2022), we noticed an error by giving the same specific name (*Circulus depressus*) to two different new described species of *Circulus* (RUBIO & ROLÁN, pp. 42 and 362).

The first species described as *Circulus depressus* on page 42 is valid, since that name has not been used previously for any other species of *Circulus*. On the contrary, the name of the second new species described as *Circulus depressus*

(page 362) is preoccupied by that previously described on page 42 and is thus not valid.

We therefore propose *Circulus mainguyi* as *nomen novum* for *Circulus depressus* Rubio & Rolán, 2022 (page 362, Fig. P9), non *Circulus depressus* Rubio & Rolán, 2022 (page 42, Fig. A13). The new specific name honours Jérôme Mainguy, assistant curator and responsible for cataloguing thousands of molluscan lots at Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

RUBIO, F. & ROLÁN, E. 2022. *New species of Vitrinellidae (Gastropoda: Truncatelloidea) from the Indo-Pacific. The genus Circulus Jeffreys, 1865.* Museo de Historia Natural. Santiago de Compostela, 422 pp.

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Figure 1. *Circulus mainguye nomen novum* for *C. depressus* n. sp. Rubio & Rolán, 2022, page 362. A: holotype, 4.03 mm in diameter, Vanuatu, N Urelapa Island, 15°36.5'S-167°02.7'E, 86-118 m; B: paratype, 3.0 mm in diameter, same data as the holotype; C: paratype, 4.0 mm, same data as the holotype; D: protoconch; E: detail of the subsutural sculpture. Non *C. depressus* Rubio & Rolán, 2022, page 42.

Figura 1. Circulus mainguye nomen novum para C. depressus n. sp. Rubio & Rolán, 2022, página 362. A: holotipo, 4,03 mm de diámetro, Vanuatu, N Urelapa Island, 15°36.5'S-167°02.7'E, 86-118 m; B: paratipo, 3,0 mm de diámetro, mismos datos que el holotipo; C: paratipo, 4,0 mm, mismos datos que el holotipo; D: protoconcha; E: detalle de la escultura subsutural. Non C. depressus Rubio & Rolán, 2022, página 42.